

Synthesis and characterization of nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of some large-ring macrocycles derived from diethylenetriamine

Anurag, Anil K. Pandey and Ram Nayan*

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001, India

E-mail : ramnayan2003@yahoo.com Fax : 91-591-2440070

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Diethylenetriamine condenses with carbon tetrachloride, tetrachloroethylene, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane, chloroform and dichloromethane in the presence of nickel(II) ions to produce macrocyclic hexaaza ligands, 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH), 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadeca-8,17-diene (HTOD), 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO), 8,16-dichloro-1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (DHCH) and 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (HACH), respectively. But, the template condensation of diethylenetriamine and chloroform in presence of copper(II) ions yields a cage-macrocycle, 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]tricosane (NACT). A blue condensed product of diethylenetriamine, dichloromethane and copper(II) ion could not be crystallized from the reaction mixture. The isolated complexes $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTOD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DHCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HACH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{NACT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_6$, and the metal-free ligand NACT.9HCl have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, melting point and spectroscopic studies.

In continuation of our recent work on large-ring macrocycles¹ in the present communication we have reported some nickel complexes of these macrocycles. The macrocycles are : 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH), 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadeca-8,17-diene (HTOD) and 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO). Also, diethylenetriamine has been condensed with dichloromethane and chloroform in the presence of copper(II) and nickel(II) ions. The generated new ligands, 8,16-dichloro-1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (DHCH), 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (HACH) and 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]tricosane (NACT), are binucleating and cage macrocycles, respectively.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The template condensation of diethylenetriamine with chlorocarbons such as carbon tetrachloride, tetrachloroethylene or 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of copper hydroxide (equimolar amounts) yields dinuclear complexes¹. The hexaaza ligand (HTCH), (HTOD) or (HTCO) is generated by condensation of two molecules of diethylenetriamine with two molecules of carbon tetrachloride, tetrachloroethylene or 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane, respectively. Similar dinuclear nickel(II) complexes of these macrocycles

have been isolated here from the nickel templated condensed mixture. Also, as expected, the macrocycles 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (HACH) and 8,16-dichloro-1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (DHCH) are generated in template condensation of diethylenetriamine with dichloromethane or chloroform in the presence of nickel hydroxide in a mixture in their equimolar amounts, respectively. In the reaction mixture, containing equimolar mixture of each reactant, cyclization proceeds due to condensation of the nickel coordinated diethylenetriamine with the chlorocarbon involving two molecules of each reactant. Each macromolecule, HTCH, HTOD, HTCO, HACH or DHCH, incorporates two metal ions in its cavity.

A 1 : 1 : 1, mixture containing copper hydroxide, diethylenetriamine and chloroform yielded a trinuclear copper(II) complex of the 'cage' macrocycle 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]tricosane (NACT). The three

Note

Table I. Analytical and physical data for the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	Colour (Colour at D.P.)	Yield (%) (M.p. °C)	Λ_M (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Found (Calcd.) %					Molecular weight Found (calcd.)
				C	H	N	Ni/Cu	Cl ^c	
[Ni ₂ (HTCH)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Brownish violet	10.04		13.90	5.61	9.78	13.60	16.40	–
C ₁₀ H ₄₈ Cl ₈ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₁₃	(Black)	(250) ^d	450	(13.94)	(5.63)	(9.76)	(13.63)	(16.46)	(861.7)
[Ni ₂ (HTOD)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₄	Violet	20.51		18.92	4.50	11.11	15.50	18.63	–
C ₁₂ H ₃₄ Cl ₈ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₆	(Black)	(248) ^d	395	(18.97)	(4.52)	(11.07)	(15.46)	(18.67)	(759.5)
[Ni ₂ (HTCO)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₄	Violet	15.79		18.93	5.02	11.00	15.44	18.61	–
C ₁₂ H ₃₈ Cl ₈ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₆	(Light green) ^a liquid	(254) ^d	430	(18.87)	(5.03)	(11.01)	(15.38)	(18.57)	(763.6)
[Ni ₂ (DHCH)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₄ ·13H ₂ O	Reddish-violet	13.72		13.28	6.93	9.32	13.07	15.72	–
C ₁₀ H ₆₃ Cl ₁₆ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₁₉	(black)	(245) ^d	510	(13.33)	(6.95)	(9.33)	(13.03)	(15.74)	(900.9)
[Ni ₂ (HACH)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₄ ·10H ₂ O	Reddish-violet	18.36		15.50	7.55	10.78	15.04	18.29	–
C ₁₀ H ₅₈ Cl ₁₄ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₁₆	(black)	(244) ^d	450	(15.44)	(7.53)	(10.81)	(15.09)	(18.23)	(778.0)
[Cu ₃ (NACT)(H ₂ O) ₃]Cl ₆	Blue	27.63		21.30	5.28	15.98	24.30	27.12	–
C ₁₄ H ₄₁ Cl ₆ Cu ₃ N ₉ O ₃	(green) ^b	(210)	718	(21.37)	(5.26)	(16.02)	(24.22)	(27.03)	(787.0)
NACT·9HCl	White	83.83	–	25.46	6.74	19.21	–	48.58	512.0
C ₁₄ S ₄₄ Cl ₉ N ₉	(black)	(145) ^d	–	(25.56)	(6.76)	(19.17)	–	(48.51)	(657.7)

^aBlack at 265°C, ^breddish-brown at 225–300°C, ^cionizable chloride ion, ^ddecomposition.

copper(II) ions are encapsulated within the cavity generated by condensation of two molecules of chloroform with three molecules of copper-coordinated diethylenetriamine.

All the complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, mass spectra, infrared and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectral studies. The results of the elemental analyses reported in Table I indicate the stoichiometry which is in agreement with the formulation given. Evidence for cyclization is demonstrated by the absence of infrared absorption bands that may be attributed to either free or coordinated NH₂ groups².

Infrared spectra :

The N–H stretching mode of the secondary amino group are seen as sharp bands at 3178, 3179, 3177, 3175, 3160 and 3142 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectra of HTCH, HTOD, HTCO, HACH, DHCH and NACT complexes, respectively. Another, medium but sharp band assigned to δ(N–H) appears at 1570–1572 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectra of nickel-hexaaza macrocyclic complexes. The corresponding peak in copper(II)-NACT system is seen at 1585 cm⁻¹ (medium, sharp). Generally sharp bands attributed to C–H function groups (asym, sym stretching, scissoring, respectively) are observed at the following frequencies (cm⁻¹) :

2924, 2877, 1450; 2924, 2877, 1385; 2922, 2876, 1483; 2925, 2865, 1478; 2916, 2865, 1480 and 2941, 2882, 1450, in the infrared spectra of metal complex of HTCH, HTOD, HTCO, HACH, DHCH and NACT, respectively. Another important weak but very sharp band in the nickel complexes at 1142–1138 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(C–H). The corresponding vibration in copper(II)-NACT system is seen as medium but very sharp band at 1146 cm⁻¹. The bonding of metal to HTCH, HTOD, HTCO, HACH, DHCH or NACT through nitrogen is indicated by bands at 409, 411, 409 (weak), 450 (very weak), 445 (shoulder) or 522 cm⁻¹ (medium but very sharp), respectively.

Coordination of water is evident by the presence of bands at 3436–3452, 3232–3321, 1600–1627, 889–658, 658–600 and 560–623 cm⁻¹ (attributed to asym, sym stretching, deformation, rocking, wagging and twisting vibrations, respectively⁹). Medium but sharp ν(Ni–O) bands, associated with coordinated water in HACH, HTCO, HTCH, DHCH, HTOD and NACT systems appear at 500, 515, 515, 518, 518 and 629 cm⁻¹, respectively. In view of the structural similarity, the infrared spectra of [Ni₂(HTCH)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄·7H₂O, [Ni₂(HTOD)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄, and [Ni₂(HTCO)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄ complexes show close correspondence in the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ region.

The infrared spectrum of metal-free ligand hydrochloride NACT·9HCl is different in several respects from the spectrum of its copper complex. The C–H stretching mode is observed as a medium but very broad band in the region

2950–2692 cm^{-1} . The $\delta(\text{C-H})$ frequency seen at high energy (1485 cm^{-1}) as compared to that in its copper complex. Also, the bands due to water molecules or copper coordinated bond with nitrogen and oxygen are absent. The cyclic nature of the ligand is demonstrated by the presence of a very weak $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band at 3150 cm^{-1} due to secondary amine group. The corresponding $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibration is seen as a medium but sharp band at 1585 cm^{-1} . Bands at 1562, 1383, 1323, 1173, 1107, 1068, 1022, 988, 947, 820, 756, 521, 470 and 424 cm^{-1} are also the characteristics of the whole ligand molecule.

- HACH (X = $-\text{CH}_2-$)
- DHCH (X = $-\text{CHCl}-$)
- HTCH (X = $-\text{CCl}_2-$)
- HTOD (X = $-\text{CCl}=\text{CCl}-$)
- HTCO (X = $-\text{CHCl}-\text{CHCl}-$)

Fig. 1. Suggested structures of the macrocyclic ligands.

The cavity size of the macrocycles HACH, DHCH and HTCH are identical. But, the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration energy in their complexes with nickel follows the order : HACH > DHCH > HTCH, and depends upon the nature of the chlorocarbon involved in the condensation. The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ at lowest energy in HTCH is due to a combined electron-withdrawing effect of the Cl atoms bound to the same carbon. This energy is increased in the complex of DHCH as the number of electron-withdrawing Cl atoms is reduced. A further increase in $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration energy in the nickel complex of HACH is due to the absence of electron-withdrawing groups in the macrocycle HACH. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$ vibrational frequencies follow the order HACH < DHCH < HTCH. Also, a decrease in the electron density on the metal due to reduction in the Ni-N bond order is expected to enhance the coordination ability of H_2O molecules as observed earlier⁶ in dimetallic copper complexes of 1,5,7,11-tetraza-6,6,12,12-tetrachlorocyclododecane (TTDE), 1,5,8,12-tetraza-6,7,13,14-tetrachlorocyclotetradecane (TTTE) and 1,5,8,12-tetraza-6,7,13,14-tetrachloro-cyclotetradeca-6,13-diene (TTTD). Thus, the $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ frequency follows the order HACH < DHCH < HTCH.

The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ or $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ vibration energies in nickel complexes of HTCO and HTOD are almost comparable as

- (1) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (X = $-\text{CCl}_2-$, n = 7)
- (2) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTOD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ (X = $-\text{CCl}=\text{CCl}-$, n = 0)
- (3) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ (X = $-\text{CHCl}-\text{CHCl}-$, n = 0)
- (4) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DHCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (X = $-\text{CHCl}-$, n = 13)
- (5) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HACH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (X = $-\text{CH}_2-$, n = 10)

- (6) $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{NACT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_6$

Fig. 2. Suggested structures of the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of the macrocyclic ligands.

the ligands are structurally similar, except the presence of two double bonds in HTOD, which may reduce the cavity size. A slightly higher energy $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration in the HTOD complex as compared to that in the HTCO complex, inspite of the electron-withdrawing effect by double bonds in the comparatively rigid HTOD molecule, indicates that the nickel(II) ion is probably well fitted in the smaller cavity of HTOD.

The three-dimensional macrocycle NACT contains one more diethylenetriamine unit than in HACH. The three copper ions accommodated in the three-dimensional cavity are strongly coordinated to the aza donors. The $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$ or $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ vibration is at much high energy as compared to $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ or $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$, respectively, in the dinuclear nickel complex of HACH. Thus, it may be concluded that the strong complexing ability of NACT or H_2O in $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{NACT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_6$ is probably due to involvement of three aza groups of NACT in coordination to each copper ion and the presence of a suitable cavity size in the cage macrocycle to encapsulate the three copper ions as well as the coordinated water molecules.

PMR spectra :

The PMR spectra of NACT.9HCl can be resolved into three distinct regions due to NH_2^+ and two non-equivalent CH_2 protons. It shows a singlet at 4.86 ppm assigned to NH_2^+ resonances. The position of the NH_2^+ proton reso-

nances is in close agreement with those reported for NH proton resonances in structurally similar aza complexes². The remaining two signals (multiplets) for the non-equivalent CH₂ protons are centered at 3.52 and 3.43 ppm. These protons are expected for the CH₂ bonded to $-\text{NH}_2^+ - \underset{\text{NH}_2^+}{\text{CH}} - \text{NH}_2^+$ - groups and the CH₂ away from

these groups, respectively. Integrations of the CH₂ signals yielding a 1 : 1 proton ratio support the structure. The CH resonance is probably obscured by the CH₂ multiplets.

Mass spectra :

The determination of the molecular weight of NACT hydrochloride by EIMS has been very useful in completing its characterization. The highest mass peak found in the spectrum is very weak and is comparable to those observed in earlier reported aza macromolecules². A low *m/z* value (Table 1) suggests that the peak is probably due to the doubly charged ion (NACT.5HCl)²⁺ which is formed after the loss of 4HCl molecules from NACT.9HCl. The fragmented 4HCl molecules may be attached the macrocycle through weak coordinate bonds. The fragmentation of HCl molecules in the mass spectrum of many other aza macromolecule hydrochlorides has been reported earlier¹.

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

All of the compounds are highly soluble in water and polar solvents such as ethanol, methanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. The molar conductivity of the complexes and the number of ionizable chloride ions in all macrocyclic molecules recorded in Table 1 are in support of their ionic structures. [Ni₂(HTCH)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄.7H₂O, [Ni₂(HTOD)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄, [Ni₂(HTCO)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄, [Ni₂(HACH)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄.10H₂O and [Ni₂(DHCH)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄.13H₂O are 4 : 1 electrolytes exhibiting molar conductance in the 395–510 range (Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹). The molar conductance value 718 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ determined for the copper-NACT complex is consistent with a 6 : 1 electrolyte. The nickel complexes are violet, reddish-violet or brownish-violet while the copper complex is blue. The metal-free ligand hydrochloride NACT.9HCl is white. All the compounds are thermally stable. The nickel complexes decompose near 250°C but the decomposition point of NACT.9HCl is comparatively very low (145°C). The [Cu₃(NACT)(H₂O)₃]Cl₆ melts at 210°C.

Experimental

Materials :

All of the solvents, reagents and metal salts used in the syntheses of metal complexes and in the preparation of

metal-free ligands were reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Measurements :

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 387 spectrophotometer using KBr disks. PMR spectra were obtained with a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz FT NMR) spectrophotometer in D₂O solution using DSS as the internal standard. A Jeol D-300 (EI/CI) mass spectrometer was used for obtaining the mass spectra of the ligand hydrochloride. Conductivity data of the complexes were recorded using their 0.01 *M* aqueous solutions, with the help of a type 304 DDR conductivity meter. Microanalyses for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were carried out at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centres, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. For obtaining nickel or copper contents of the complexes, they were decomposed by strong heating in presence of fusion mixture and the metal contents were determined by EDTA titration³.

General synthetic procedure :

Template synthesis of nickel(II) or copper(II) macrocyclic complexes were carried out in 200 mL *n*-butanol/methanol as solvent. The products extracted in water were recovered by concentration and refrigeration, and were purified by treatment with organic solvents, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complexes of hexaaza macrocycles :

The nickel(II) complex of 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadeca-8,17-diene (HTOD) was prepared by heating equimolar mixture of diethylenetriamine (5.56 g, 53.89 mmol) and tetrachloroethylene (8.94 g, 53.91 mmol) in the presence of nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.92 mmol) in butanol. The condensation reaction was very slow (> 13 h) with colour change from green to pink. The cooled refluxed mixture was stirred with 100 mL of water for about 10 min and filtered. The green residue was rejected and the yellowish-red aqueous layer was separated from the non-aqueous red layer. Concentration, chilling and evaporation under reduced pressure of the yellowish-red aqueous solution caused a brownish-violet sticky solid. The sticky matter was removed by a benzene-ether (1 : 1) mixture as described in previous systems¹. The product was further dissolved in 100 mL volume of methanol. Acetone (100 mL) was added dropwise with stirring, resulting in the precipitation of violet macrocyclic complex [Ni₂(HTOD)(H₂O)₆]Cl₄. The product was filtered, washed with acetone-methanol (1 : 1) mixture, and the yellowish-red filtrate was rejected. The violet powder finally washed with ether was dried under reduced pressure, yield 4.20 g.

For the syntheses of the nickel(II) complexes of 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO), 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (HACH) or 8,16-dichloro-1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaazacyclohexadecane (DHCH), the 1 : 1 : 1, mixture of nickel hydroxide, diethylenetriamine and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (9.05 g), dichloromethane (5.50 g) or chloroform (7.72 g) prepared in butanol was refluxed for 2 h. The light green colour of the reaction mixture containing 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane changed immediately to red within 10 min and finally to a mixture of a violet precipitate and reddish-violet solution. In the dichloromethane system a light green precipitate formed in the mixture turned milky-green after shaking for 2 min. The resulting milky-green mixture changed to a violet solution consisting a green precipitate after heating. The light green precipitate of the corresponding mixture in chloroform system gradually changed to pinkish-violet precipitate during first 15 min of heating. Finally, it changed to a light violet precipitate after 2 h of heating. Each refluxed mixture was allowed to cool and impure violet-red crystals of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ (slightly soluble in methanol) and reddish-violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HACH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DHCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained as described in HTOD system. The violet-red product and the $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HACH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were washed with small amount of methanol followed by acetone. Analytically pure violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4$ and reddish-violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HACH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DHCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were finally obtained by washing with ether and drying under reduced pressure (yield 3.25, 4.62 and 0.40 g for HTCO, HACH and DHCH complexes, respectively).

A stirred equimolar mixture of nickel hydroxide, diethylenetriamine and carbon tetrachloride (9.95 g) in 200 mL methanol was refluxed for 2 h 15 min for obtaining the nickel(II) complex of 1,4,7,9,12,15-hexaaza-8,8,16,16-tetrachlorocyclohexadecane (HTCH). The light green precipitate initially formed in the mixture changed to brown within 10 min, and then to dark reddish-brown at the end of heating. The brownish-violet sticky crystals of the product $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{HTCH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were recovered from the refluxed mixture as in above systems and were purified first by removing sticky material by benzene-ether treatment as described earlier¹ and then washing with methanol (small quantity, in order to avoid loss of product due to its high solubility in the solvent) followed by ether. After drying under reduced pressure analytically pure crystals of the complex were obtained, yield 2.80 g.

Synthesis of the copper(II) complex of 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]tricosane (NACT) :

The product was obtained from template condensation between diethylenetriamine and chloroform in presence of copper hydroxide (equimolar mixture, chloroform 8.57 g). The blue reaction mixture in butanol was heated to reflux for 7 h. The blue solution changed to a deep blue solution after being refluxed for 10 min and, subsequently, fine bluish-violet crystals were deposited in the flask after 1 h of heating. Finally, at the end of the heating the whole mass turned into a dirty yellowish-blue turbid mixture. The product was extracted in 150 mL water as usual. The concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous extract yielded greenish-blue sticky crystals. The sticky material was removed by ether-benzene (1 : 1) mixture as described in other systems. The blue crystals of $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{NACT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_6$ were finally washed with methanol followed by ether and dried (yield 5.2 g).

Preparation of 2,5,8,10,13,16,17,20,23-nonaazabicyclo[7.7.7]-tricosane hydrochloride (NACT.9HCl) :

The macrocyclic product $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{NACT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\text{Cl}_6$ (3.00 g, 3.81 mmol) was dissolved in 100 mL water. Metal-free aqueous solution of the ligand hydrochloride was obtained as described earlier¹. The colourless aqueous solution was concentrated and kept for crystallization for 15 days at room temperature. The solution yielded a light yellow semi-solid. A white powder settled down after the solid was stirred with 50 mL methanol for 5 min. The product then filtered and washed with methanol was collected, yield 2.10 g.

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References

1. M. Singh and R. Nayan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1999, **29**, 1395.
2. M. Singh and R. Nayan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1997, **27**, 619; 1998, **28**, 87; M. S. Holtman and S. C. Cummings, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 660; M. Singh, Anurag and R. Nayan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 1703; S. C. Jackels, K. Farmery, E. K. Barefield, N. J. Rose and D. H. Bush, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2893.
3. J. Bassett, R. C. Denny, G. H. Jeffery and J. Mendham, "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Group Ltd., London, 1978.